

CLARIFICATIONS ON THE *FINGER BALL* AND ITS DIDACTIC- PEDAGOGICAL APPLICATION IN SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the topic of Finger Ball, aiming to clarify its application in the practices of Physical Education in schools, exploring the pedagogical and didactic aspects of the action itself. It is a subject of extreme scientific, theoretical, and empirical relevance because it opens up spaces for teaching proposals, observation from diverse areas of knowledge, and self-learning. Its epistemic relevance lies in the fact that it provides conditions to explore behavioral spaces and, through playful intervention, understand intrinsic processes and develop intervention mechanisms that improve aspects related to cognitive fields. This is a theoretical essay, produced from applied experiences that were subsequently analyzed, leading to deductions and conclusions about the impact of the activity on the motor development processes of the students who participated. Finger Ball is a game of skill and motor coordination that simulates a miniature football match. Designed for all ages, it provides fun, a sense of competition, and coordinated psychomotor stimulation, representing an innovative and accessible pedagogical approach that expands the possibilities of experiencing sports in the school environment, with the aim of cognitive and intellectual development.

Keywords: Finger Ball. Playfulness. School Physical Education. Psychomotor development.

INTRODUCTION

There is a pressing need to create didactic and educational methodologies and strategies aimed at expanding the psychomotor development capacity of students beyond the usual exercises of coloring, using playdough, origami, and cutting in the classroom. All of these are well-established activities that have proven their efficiency and effectiveness in terms of

learning; however, what is sought beyond this is the student's interaction with the developmental process of their cognitive capacity, carried out in a dynamic and interactive way.

In this space of ideas and teaching strategies, we have the *Finger Ball*, also known as *Finger football, or finger soccer*, is a game of skill and motor coordination that simulates a miniature soccer match. It is designed for all ages, providing fun, a competitive spirit, and coordinated psychomotor stimulation. The set consists of a soccer field printed on a sturdy cardboard box, which functions as both the game board and playing area. The design is practical, lightweight, and portable, allowing the game to be used in classrooms, homes, school recreation, and leisure time.

The components needed to make the toy are a reinforced cardboard box printed with official mini-soccer field markings, fixed or attachable goalposts made of popsicle sticks, and a plastic ping pong ball suitable for the size of the field. Ideally, the dimensions of the field and goalposts should be objective metric replicas of an official soccer field, as this would teach students rules of proportionality, scales, official measurements, and parallels. Beyond the game itself, there is a whole didactic-pedagogical concern in providing conditions for learning and multidisciplinary cognitive development.

School Physical Education, as a pedagogical curricular component committed to the integral formation of students, has as one of its fundamental principles the promotion of the expansion of cognitive development capacity through didactic actions and interactions, by enhancing the use of bodily practices in the expression and acquisition of knowledge.

In this context, it becomes essential to develop pedagogical proposals that consider the diversity of thought and corporeality, overcoming teaching and learning models based exclusively on physical performance and the standardization of motor gestures. Activities should strengthen participants' logical reasoning, techniques, and strategies for overcoming challenges and increasing their willingness to participate.

Regarding the objectives of the impact of applying Finger Ball (finger soccer) in school Physical Education classes, there is interest in the development of students' gross and fine motor coordination. In the process of studying this condition, the aim is to investigate the effects of playing the game on the development of fine motor coordination, with emphasis on finger movement control, precision, laterality, and eye-hand coordination in students.

Furthermore, the intention is to verify the contributions of Finger Ball to the improvement of gross motor coordination, considering aspects such as posture, balance, spatial organization, and trunk control during the game. Additionally, a specific objective is to analyze how pedagogical adaptations of Finger Ball favor the participation of students with different

levels of motor skills in the context of school Physical Education, identifying possible changes in student engagement, autonomy, and self-esteem resulting from the integrative pedagogical experience promoted through the game.

Finger *Ball* is a didactic-pedagogical activity presented as a tool to promote cognitive development that can be applied to students of any age/grade level, with different interests regarding psychomotor performance, after careful analysis of individual conditions. It is always necessary to clarify that Physical Education in schools is a science that is based on empirical data to develop its actions and, in this process, arrives at conclusions about which mechanisms to apply to situations diagnosed as amenable to intervention by Physical Education professionals in partnership with professionals from the fields of Psychomotricity, Psychopedagogy, Pedagogy, Medicine, Physiotherapy, and Occupational Therapy.

CLARIFICATIONS REGARDING THE EMPIRICAL APPLICATION OF THE FINGER BOLL

Since finger ball is a strictly empirical didactic-pedagogical activity, and its practical application gives rise to analytical studies, approximations, and conclusions, it is possible to theorize and thus clarify its epistemic dimensions. In this sense, this text seeks to explain the conditions that must be strictly followed regarding the application of the game, depending on the teacher's interest.

The player uses their index fingers and thumbs to represent the player, propelling the ball across the field with a flick (a quick touch) followed by a flick of the ball. The objective is to score goals against the opponent by performing quick touches, passes, and shots, using only their fingers. To increase the difficulty, each player only has a goalkeeper who can be moved after the opponent's first touch, reducing the angle of the penalty area.

Finger ball represents an innovative and accessible pedagogical approach that expands the possibilities for experiencing sports in the school environment, with the aim of cognitive and intellectual development. As an adaptation of traditional football, it allows students to understand the basic principles of the classic sport, such as rules, strategies, cooperation, respect, and decision-making. It can also be adapted to a playful dimension, where a group of specialists from different areas related to psychomotor skills can be organized to develop a set of details to be observed during practice and discussed *afterward* for theoretical study purposes.

The practice of Finger Ball aims to promote the development of fine motor coordination, laterality, action strategy, concentration, logical reasoning, and action planning, as well as

stimulating socio-emotional skills such as teamwork, self-control, and conflict resolution. Because it does not require a large physical space or intense physical effort, it becomes a viable alternative for a wide variety of school contexts, including classrooms, small spaces, and adverse weather conditions.

Many schools lack adequate physical spaces for physical education practices, and on days of intense heat or rain, the entire process is compromised, requiring adaptations, many of them absurd and improvised. With finger ball, these unplanned situations can be addressed, since, being a pedagogical activity with a clear and dynamic teaching methodology, it can be implemented in any environment without overly complex requirements.

The application of finger balls in the context of school physical education.

Finger Football is presented as a pedagogical adaptation of football that allows for the experience of the sport from a cognitive educational perspective, shifting the focus from strength, speed, and physical endurance to aspects such as decision-making, strategic planning, fine motor coordination, and social interaction. This characteristic broadens access to sports practice, favoring the participation of students with disabilities, developmental disorders, motor difficulties, as well as those who show resistance or insecurity towards traditional sports.

The application of Finger Ball in the context of school Physical Education aims to contribute to the construction of an equitable pedagogical environment, in which the rules, materials, and organization of the game can be easily adapted to the needs of the students. These possibilities for adaptation allow the didactic assumptions of education to be seen and interpreted not as limitations, but as an elementary constitutive element of the formal educational process.

In addition to promoting inclusion, Finger Ball fosters learning related to the conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal dimensions of the sport, in accordance with the guidelines of the Brazilian National Curriculum Base (BNCC). The practice encourages understanding of the rules, strategies, and internal logic of the game, while simultaneously promoting values such as autonomy and conflict resolution, fundamental aspects for healthy coexistence in the school environment.

From a methodological point of view, Finger Boll is a viable and accessible proposal, which can be developed with low-cost materials and in small spaces, thus broadening its applicability in different school settings, especially in the public school system.

Its strategic application in basic education is justified by the possibility of deepening systematic studies on pedagogical practices through the teaching of sports, especially football, contributing to the broad production of scientific knowledge that supports teaching actions that are more sensitive to learning, committed to the subjective right of all students to participation and cognitive development in and through Physical Education at school.

Impact of Fingerball on Gross and Fine Motor Coordination

Human neuropsychomotor development is a crucial stage of existence, presenting a very narrow window of opportunity that must be optimized and explored to the fullest extent through strategies that prove to be of a pedagogical nature; because it is not enough for the individual to learn the thing itself, it is important that they understand the entire process, even if it does not make sense to them at that moment; but so that those who accompany or coordinate the actions can take them as objects of systematic study in future situations.

The acquisition of motor coordination is one of the central elements of children's motor development and plays a fundamental role in students' learning and participation in all school physical activities, from writing to broader movements. In the context of inclusive Physical Education, *for example*, it becomes relevant to propose activities that stimulate both gross motor coordination, related to large muscle groups and broad movements, and fine motor coordination, associated with the precise control of movements performed mainly with hands and fingers.

Finger football, by requiring actions such as body positioning, postural stability, force control, direction, and precision of finger movements, contributes precisely and directly to the improvement of fine motor coordination. These demands favor the development of neuromotor control, movement dissociation, laterality, and eye-hand coordination, essential aspects for educational and functional activities such as writing, handling objects, and performing daily school tasks.

Although characterized by predominantly fine motor movements, Finger Ball also impacts gross motor coordination by mobilizing postural adjustments, trunk control, spatial organization, and orientation within the playing space. Maintaining proper posture, regulating muscle tone, and interacting with the environment and peers require the participation of large muscle groups, promoting integration between the motor, perceptual, and cognitive systems.

From an inclusive perspective, Finger Ball allows for pedagogical adaptations that respect the different rhythms and motor abilities of students, permitting gradual progressions in

motor complexity. Students with difficulties in gross or fine motor coordination can actively participate in the game, experiencing situations that promote and strengthen their autonomy and self-esteem.

The application of Finger Ball in Physical Education shows significant potential for the integrated development of gross and fine motor coordination, establishing itself as a relevant pedagogical strategy for promoting broad learning, focusing on neuropsychomotor development and student engagement. Investigating these impacts within a didactic-pedagogical project and its subsequent systematic discussion contributes to deepening discussions on alternative methodologies applied to sports teaching and on body practices that favor broad motor development in diverse educational contexts.

Motivations for Producing the Essay

This essay was conceived from the need to consider strategies that provide didactic support to school Physical Education teachers, seeking to expand their practice as a space for the production of knowledge, pedagogical practices, and educational processes committed to the integral development of students. This thinking recognizes the school as an environment marked by the opportunity for the production of knowledge, innovations, and bodily experiences, requiring methodological proposals that break with technicist curricular models regarding the teaching of sports.

The motivation for producing this work stems from the increasingly pressing need to deepen research into pedagogical practices in sports education, especially those that enable the effective participation of students with different levels of motor skills. It is observed that, in the daily school routine, traditional sports education still prioritizes *performance* and technical execution, which can limit access for some students to meaningful bodily experiences.

unique scenario, Finger Ball (finger football) is proposed as a pedagogical strategy aligned with the assumptions of developing critical thinking about the act of teaching and learning from experience, providing high-value scientific research by reinterpreting the sport from an accessible and adaptable approach. Furthermore, the choice of Finger Ball as the object of exploration for this essay is related to the interest in understanding the impacts of adapted sports practices on the development of gross and fine motor coordination, a relevant theme in the field of school Physical Education and still little explored from an empirical perspective. In this sense, it seeks to articulate motor development, pedagogical practices, and analytical processes, contributing directly to scientific debates and productions.

Finger Football is a pedagogical adaptation of traditional football, developed with the aim of expanding the possibilities of sports experiences in Physical Education at school in an accessible way. The creation and adaptation process was based on reinterpreting the logic of the game, maintaining its fundamental principles, such as rules, strategies and decision-making, transferring motor execution to controlled finger movements.

The creativity and innovation of Finger Boll lie in its character as a low-cost educational technology, built with simple materials that can be found anywhere, allowing for its broad and unrestricted replicability in different school contexts. It represents a pedagogical and social innovation, reorganizing the sport to favor the participation of students with different levels of motor skills.

From a methodological point of view, the nature of its proposal is applied progressively, beginning with the exploration of the material, explanation and understanding of the rules, followed by adaptable technical and strategic challenges. The teaching methodology is based on active methodologies, with the teacher acting as coordinator of the entire process, promoting the development of conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal dimensions.

Regarding the playful nature of Finger Boll, it is always worth clarifying that playfulness represents a profound research methodology and that, for its realization, it is necessary to develop a broad, well-structured and rigorous scientific project with strictly defined objectives regarding what is intended to be observed, accompanied by a multidisciplinary team of experts, each equipped with an observation guide that, at the end of the entire process, will serve as a basis for detecting possible problems of various kinds, as well as for the development of intervention procedures in the neuropsychomotor and cognitive fields.

Regarding its competitive nature, it encourages participants to develop strategies for advancing and overcoming the challenges that arise throughout the game, having to surpass their opponent in techniques through intelligent and aesthetically elaborate plays, with a view to winning the match. To this end, players must prove themselves creative, enhancing engagement and entertainment, where these actions function as a motivating element in the teaching and self-learning process.

Finger Boll is also particularly relevant in serving students with Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) **and** other neurodevelopmental disorders, such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) and Developmental Coordination Disorder (DCD). The game's structure, based on short-duration challenges, clear rules, stimulation of focused attention, and movement control, promotes self-regulation, concentration, and decision-making—aspects

frequently compromised in individuals with these conditions. Furthermore, the possibility of adapting the pace, rules, and active teacher participation contributes to the active and meaningful participation of these students in Physical Education classes.

From a pedagogical point of view, Finger Ball is a viable, low-cost educational product that is easy to develop and replicate, especially in the context of public schools or even outside of them, whether in communities or at home. Its application allows the construction of equitable learning environments, in which differences related to motor, cognitive, and attentional development are understood as a constitutive part of the educational process and not as impediments to participation.

This study contributes to the fields of school Physical Education, Psychomotricity, Pedagogy, Psychopedagogy, and Childcare by expanding discussions on methodologies that broaden the spectrum of inclusion and the production of new knowledge about sports teaching, offering theoretical and methodological support based on empiricism for teaching practice with students of diverse physical and neurological backgrounds. As an educational product, the Finger Ball has the potential to inspire new pedagogical practices and future scientific investigations of an empirical and theoretical nature [*analytical, interpretive, deductive*], expanding and strengthening Physical Education's commitment to innovation, experience, and the quality inherent in the formal educational process.

EXPECTED RESULTS WITH THE PRACTICAL APPLICATION OF FINGER BALL

Like any product of an empirical nature, the systematized application of Finger Ball (finger football) in school Physical Education classes refers to a direct induction on the target object of study and, it is expected that this action will contribute significantly to the development of neuromotor aspects, such as gross and fine motor coordination of students, showing advances in the control of finger movements, precision of gestures, eye-hand coordination and laterality. It is already recognized as a fact that such improvements tend to reflect very positively in relation to other school activities that require precision motor skills, such as writing, drawing, coloring drawings, cutting and handling didactic materials of various pedagogical natures, such as collages and weavings.

Specifically regarding gross motor coordination, practicing Finger Ball helps develop and identify progress related to postural control, balance, spatial organization, and muscle tone regulation, resulting from the bodily demands present during the game. Although fine motor

skills are prioritized during the action, maintaining posture and interacting with space and peers indicate an integrated impact on overall motor development.

From the perspective of general educational inclusion, it is expected that Finger Ball will promote greater participation of students with different levels of motor skills, reducing barriers to sports practice and promoting an integrated pedagogical environment based on an equitable vision of education. The possibility of adapting rules, materials, and playing time tends to increase engagement, autonomy, and the sense of belonging of students, especially those with motor difficulties or specific educational needs.

The proposal contributes to strengthening attitudes related to cooperation, mutual respect, and conflict resolution, fundamental aspects of the attitudinal dimension of sport, according to the guidelines of the National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC). In this sense, Finger Ball can be consolidated as a pedagogical strategy that redefines the teaching of sport in Physical Education, shifting the focus from *performance* towards learning as well.

The results obtained from the empirical application of the Finger Ball practice broaden the scope of the research, resulting in a wide and deep production of knowledge in the area of School Physical Education, offering theoretical and methodological support for teachers and coaches seeking inclusive and innovative pedagogical practices, as well as contributing to future investigations on sports adaptations and psychomotor development in the educational context.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The application of Finger Ball (finger football) as a didactic-pedagogical strategy in Physical Education at school, with an emphasis on the development of gross and fine motor coordination, reveals itself as an opportunity for the expansion and deepening of studies, resulting in the promotion of inclusive practices through sports.

The theoretical and methodological foundations presented indicate that adapting traditional football to a broad and accessible format, within the realm of playfulness and pedagogically oriented, allows for a redefinition of sports education, shifting the focus from physical performance to learning, participation, and the holistic development of students.

The proposal is directly related to the guidelines of the Brazilian National Common Curriculum Base (BNCC), as it encompasses the conceptual, procedural, and attitudinal dimensions of sport, promoting learning related to cooperation, respect for rules, autonomy, and conflict resolution. The expected impacts on gross and fine motor coordination reinforce

the potential of Finger Ball as a methodological resource for integrated motor development, including in inclusive education contexts.

All of the above is evidenced by experiences conducted with students in regular full-time schools, where data was collected by the teacher and subsequently analyzed, discussed, and presented in the form of a scientific synthesis, resulting in this essay. Much remains to be explored, especially regarding the playful aspect, which reveals the greatest potential, and therefore, other didactic and conceptual parameters must be developed.